

Digital Dilemmas:

and the Invisible Biases

AI

Do you ever use:

- **Netflix's** recommendations to pick a new series?
- **Siri** or **Google Assistant** to control your phone while driving?
- **ChatGPT** to write a text?

Then you're using artificial intelligence!

Artificial intelligence, which learns from our data, conveniently takes tasks out of our hands. But there is a risk in this help: **bias**.

For example, systems like Siri and Alexa sometimes struggle with dialects and have trouble recognizing female voices. And ChatGPT sometimes makes **inappropriate, racist** or **sexist statements**.

So, even though artificial intelligence seems **very useful**, it can also lead to **undesirable situations**.
Can we use artificial intelligence if it also makes mistakes?

- Find out more** about artificial intelligence:
- o Look through the eyes of artificial intelligence
 - o Read what Husein, Martha, Evelien, Kaan and Michel think about artificial intelligence
 - o Help build a neural network
 - o Leave your opinion on the message board!

